

X-RAY CT IMAGE-BASED MEASUREMENT AND MODELING OF MICROSCOPIC DEFECTS IN CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to develop a method to measure the microscopic defects in CFRP laminates from X-ray computed tomography (CT) images and a method to introduce the effect of the defects to the finite element method. In the method, voids and fiber distortion are considered. Voids are detected using the difference of the brightness of the X-ray CT images. Fiber distortion is analyzed by processing acquired tomographic images by digital image correlation method (DIC). In order to assess the validity of the proposed method, this study applied the proposed method to a quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate. After X-ray CT imaging, the sample was sectioned and polished. The fiber orientation was then measured experimentally using microscopy. The fiber orientation calculated using the proposed method agrees very well with the experimentally measured one. After demonstrating the validity of the proposed method, we applied the method to the composite lattice cylindrical structure for launch vehicle. This structure was fabricated by a low-cost manufacturing technique. Fiber distortions and voids were measured by the proposed method, and the effect of the defects was introduced to the finite element model. The material properties predicted by the finite element analysis agreed well with the experimental result. The results proved that the proposed method can measure the microscopic defect and can predict the effect of the defect by using FEM.

1 INTRODUCTION

In aerospace industry, light weight structure is necessary for reducing fuel consumption. Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is being commonly used because of its high strength-weight and stiffness-weight ratio. Nowadays, prepreg-autoclave manufacturing process is widely used to produce composite structure in aerospace industry. Although it can produce CFRP with good and stable quality, it is high-cost process.

In order to reduce manufacturing cost, Out-of-Autoclave (OoA) methods have been developed [1-2]. Application of CFRP made by OoA method is increasingly expanding to aircraft and spacecraft structure. For example, Proton-M, a Russian space launch vehicle, has anisogrid (anisotropic grid) lattice structure for the payload adapter and the interstages [3-5]. The lattice structure was

manufactured by one of OoA methods called continuous wet filament winding and the manufacturing cost was 30% less than the conventional structure made of aluminum alloy [5]. Although practical use of CFRP lattice structures is limited so far, a number of researches related to lattice structure are being carried out all over the world. Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) is trying to apply lattice cylinder made of wet winding method to space launcher's adapter between the fuel tank and the payload (Fig.1) [6].

Fig. 1 Lattice cylinder produced by JAXA and broken ribs after compressive test.

The drawback of OoA methods is the possibility of unexpected microscopic defects such as voids and fiber misalignment in produced CFRP which are caused by relatively low pressure during the hardening process. The ribs of the lattice cylinder made by wet winding process in JAXA shown in Fig.2 have voids between carbon fiber tows and fiber misalignment. B. Budiansky et al. [7] presented a review of experimental data and elementary theoretical formulas for compressive failure of polymer matrix fiber composites which indicates that the dominant failure mode is by plastic kinking and initial local fiber misalignment plays a central role in the plastic kinking process. It is obvious that the impact of microscopic defects should not be ignored in order to precisely predict properties of CFRP.

Fig. 2 Tomographic image of the lattice rib produced by an OoA methods

An effective method to consider defects is finite element analysis using a three-dimensional finite element model constructed by stacking micro-focus X-ray computed tomographic images, which contain actual microscopic defects. Images taken by X-ray CT are expressed in gray scale, and the brightness of each pixel depends on the X-ray absorption coefficient of the object. Carbon fiber and matrix in CFRP have similar absorption coefficient, resulting in indistinctive contrast between two elements. Thanks to the recent improvement of X-ray CT scanner, images with better resolution and contrast can be obtained. Researchers are now able to generate the finite element model of CFRP. Voxel methods are often utilized for considering microscopic defects. In this method, one voxel is defined to be one element and the properties of carbon fiber or resin are assigned. Green et al. [8] proved by this method that the idealization of straight warp and weft yarns in three-dimensional woven composites had been an oversimplification and the finite element model considering the yarns' waviness gave the result closer to that of the experiment. Czabaj et al. [9] succeeded in generating the three-dimensional model of tiny unidirectional graphite/epoxy composite which was numerically reconstructed based on high-resolution tomography images and had precise fiber orientation thanks to their segmentation algorithm. However, these voxel methods are not suitable for the simulation with

relatively large structure that can be practically used. Such simulations demand too many numbers of the elements and are not feasible in terms of calculation cost.

This paper aims to develop a method to measure the microscopic defects in CFRP laminates from X-ray CT images and a method to introduce the effect of the defects to the finite element method. In the method, voids and fiber distortion are considered. Voids are detected using the difference of the brightness of the X-ray CT images. Fiber distortion is analyzed by processing acquired tomographic images by digital image correlation method (DIC). After demonstrating the validity of the proposed method, we applied the method to the composite lattice cylindrical structure for launch vehicle.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the methods to measure and consider the microscopic defects is described and validated. In the section 3, the proposed method is applied to the CFRP lattice cylindrical structure. Conclusions from this study are drawn in the last section.

2 ANALYTICAL METHOD

2.1 Method

This section describes the method to measure the microscopic defects from the X-ray CT images. In this study, voids and fiber distortion are considered. Regarding to voids, the brightness of the void region on the X-ray CT image is sufficiently low compared with fiber and resin region (see Fig. 2). Therefore, the void content can be analysed by binarizing the image by setting threshold of brightness. Before the binarization, the images are processed by Gaussian filter in order to mitigate the effect of noise. Figure 3 shows the example of one element processed by Gaussian filter and binarization. We set the threshold value 110 in this case so that the shape of voids could be kept unchanged.

Fig. 3 Original CT image (a), after processed by Gaussian filter (b) and after binarization (c)

On the other hand, three-dimensional fiber orientation distribution must be acquired in order to measure fiber distortion. However, it is difficult to distinguish fibers clearly from resin based on X-ray tomography because carbon fibers and matrix resin have similar radiodensities. For that reason, in this study, the brightness pattern on the X-ray CT image which results from the arrangement of the fibers and resin is traced. Figure 4 presents the concept of the proposed method: fiber patterns in different cross-sectional images of the CFRP laminate are compared. Then a subset having similar brightness patterns is sought using DIC. In the DIC calculation, two tomographic images are regarded as virtual surfaces before and after deformation. The in-plane displacement of the subset, which has similar brightness pattern, is calculated between the two surfaces. For Fig. 4, the in-plane subset displacement vector is (a, c) . The distance between the two sections is b , and the 3D fiber orientation vector of this subset is (a, b, c) . In addition, the contrast on the X-ray CT image need not be strong for the proposed method. Even if fiber and resin cannot be digitalized clearly, the brightness pattern can be traced using DIC [10].

When the subset distance vector is (a, c) , 3D fiber orientation vector of this subset is (a, b, c) .

Fig. 4 Schematic of the concept of the fiber orientation measuring method

2.2 Validation of the method

By using the proposed method, voids and fiber orientation can be measured. Measuring technique for the void is very clear. On the other hand, that for fiber orientation is novel method. Therefore it must be validated. In this section, measuring technique of the fiber orientation is validated by comparing results between the proposed method and direct measurement.

The quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate stacking configuration of $[45/0/45/90]_{4s}$, using T800S/#3900-2B prepreps (Toray Industries, Inc.), was used for the test. Dimensions of the specimen were 2 mm×2 mm square, 6 mm in thickness. Tomographic images of CFRP laminates were acquired using a micro-focus X-ray CT device (MicroXCT-200; Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH). These images were combined and reconstructed to produce a 3D image of the sample. After X-ray CT imaging, the acquired CT images were reconstructed (VGStudioMAX2.2; Volume Graphics GmbH). Then sectional images perpendicular to the nominal fiber orientation were obtained. Figure 5 portrays two of the reconstructed CT images. Correlation of the brightness pattern of different section images was calculated using DIC. Then the fiber orientations were acquired using the method proposed in section 2.1. Correlation computations were performed in the following conditions. The subset size was 17×17 pixels. The center of the subset was stepped by every 10 pixels. A program developed by Yoneyama et al. [11] for DIC was used for calculation of the correlation between images.

After X-ray CT imaging, the specimen was molded into epoxy resin and was polished to yield a section micrograph of the section perpendicular to the through-the-thickness direction. Using this section micrograph, fiber orientations were acquired.

Fig. 5 X-ray CT images of CFRP sample

Sections labeled 'a' and 'b' in Fig. 5 were chosen for comparing the fiber orientations. Figure 6 shows each section micrograph superposed by the fiber orientation calculated by the proposed method. The calculated fiber orientation agreed very well. This result demonstrates that the proposed method can calculate the correct fiber orientation qualitatively. It is noteworthy that when fiber orientation vectors were superposed onto the section micrograph, they were rotated about 3 deg for section 'a' and about 2 deg for section 'b' because the X-ray CT images and section micrographs were taken from slightly different angles. The mean fiber orientation and standard deviation were acquired using the proposed method. Those measured from section micrographs are presented in Table 1. The calculated and measured mean values were slightly different from one another, but the difference was approximately equal to the angle to which the vectors had been rotated when they were superposed onto the micrograph. Standard deviations agreed well, especially in section 'b'. The discussion presented above demonstrated that, using the proposed method, the fiber orientation was correctly measured directly from X-ray CT images.

Fig. 6 Section micrographs superposed by calculated fiber orientations.

Table 1 Average and standard deviation of measured fiber orientations.

Section and method	Average θ [°]	Standard deviation
Section a, DIC	42.83	1.520
Section a, Micrograph	45.69	1.349
Section b, DIC	43.95	1.142
Section b, Micrograph	46.01	1.150

3 APPLICATION TO THE LATTICE CYLINDRICAL STRUCTURE

3.1 Material

The proposed method was applied to the lattice cylindrical structure for the launch vehicle (Fig. 1). The ribs of length of 64mm were cut from a segment from the lattice cylindrical structure (Fig. 7). This lattice cylinder was manufactured by wet winding process. In the process carbon fiber tows impregnated with wet resin are wound around the silicon mold on the mandrel and cured using the differential pressure between a vacuum and atmosphere under the vacuum bag. The materials used for the lattice composite were standard modulus type carbon fiber (Toho Tenax STS40 (24K)) and thermo-setting epoxy resin system (Nagase ChemteX DENATITE T-769/R3290). Three specimens from seventeen were chosen and named TP1, TP2 and TP3. In this study, finite element models of these three specimens were created. After the finite element modeling, four point bending tests were carried out for fifteen specimens including TP1, TP2 and TP3. The bending moduli were compared between finite element models and experimental results. The remaining two specimens were used for the observation of the cross sections in order to calculate fiber volume fraction.

Fig. 7 A segment of lattice cylindrical structure and location of each specimen

3.2 Method

Figure 8 explains the overview of the methodology for calculating bending modulus by using FEM. First the size of the model and the finite element was defined. The span of the model was defined to be 51 mm that is equal to the distance between supporting points in four point bending test for reducing simulation cost. The lengths in x direction and y direction were defined to be about 11.7mm and 3.43mm respectively. Then the box was divided into 43008 C3D20R elements. The actual dimension of one element is about 245 μ m in x and y direction, and about 789 μ m in z direction.

Tomographic images of TP1, TP2 and TP3 were acquired by X-ray computed tomography. CT images were taken by the X-ray CT device used in section 2.2. It would be desirable that CT images were taken all over the specimen, but it was not viable because it took too much time. Therefore we divided the model into three large parts and the small part in each large part highlighted by white shown in Fig. 9 was selected as representative. Tomographic images were taken only for the representative parts, and we assumed that the rest of each large part had the same material properties as those of the representative part. Void size and location, fiber orientation at each point in the three parts were calculated using the method described in the section 2.1.

Fig. 8 Overview of proposed methodology for creating finite element model

Fig. 9 Finite element model of the specimen and the tomography locations

Each element was assumed to be orthotropic. Components of the stiffness matrix were calculated in each element from Halpin-Tsai's equations and material properties of fiber and matrix. G_{23} was calculated by the relation between G_{23} , E_2 and ν_{23} as the specimen was transversely isotropic about the fiber direction. Let E_L^f , E_T^f , G_{LT}^f , E^m , ν_{LT}^f , ν_{TT}^f , ν^m denote Young's modulus of fiber in fiber direction, Young's modulus of fiber in transverse direction, Shear modulus of fiber in fiber-transverse directions, Young's modulus of matrix, Poisson's ratio of fiber in fiber-transverse directions, Poisson's ratio of fiber in transverse-transverse directions and Poisson's ratio of matrix, respectively. Elastic constants of an element are calculated by,

$$E_1 = E_L^f V_f + E^m V_m \quad (1)$$

$$\nu_{12} = \nu_{LT}^f V_f + \nu^m V_m \quad (2)$$

$$M/M^m = (1 + \xi \eta V_f) / (1 - \eta V_f) \text{ where}$$

$$(M, M^f, M^m) = (E_2, E_T^f, E^m), (G_{12}, G_{LT}^f, G^m), (\nu_{23}, \nu_{TT}^f, \nu^m) \text{ and} \quad (3)$$

$$\eta = (M^f/M^m - 1) / (M^f/M^m + 1)$$

$$G_{23} = E_2 / 2(1 + \nu_{23}) \quad (4)$$

where ξ is a parameter representing the extent of reinforcement of the composites and differs depending on loading conditions. We assumed $\xi=2.0$ in calculating E_2 and $\xi=1.0$ in calculating G_{12} and ν_{23} .

In Halpin-Tsai's equations, fiber and matrix volume fraction (V_f and V_m) must be calculated. In this study, volume fraction of voids V_v can be calculated from the method described in section 2.1. Therefore if the ratio of V_f to V_m is known, we can calculate the V_f and V_m from,

$$V_f + V_m + V_v = 1 \quad (5)$$

In this research, we introduce two approaches to acquire the ratio. The first approach assumes that the ratio of V_f to V_m is uniform all over the specimen. Cross sectional micrograph of a rib was obtained by

polishing specimen 6 (Fig. 7). The micrograph was binarized and we calculated the ratio of V_f to V_m . Elasticity constants of TP1 were calculated by this global V_f approach. The second approach, the ratio was calculated from the CT image element by element. Average brightness of the certain area of the CT image relates to the ratio of V_f to V_m because fiber and matrix have slightly different radiodensities. Therefore in this approach, we made a calibration relationship between the averaged brightness and the V_f/V_m ratio by using specimen 9 in Fig. 7. Figure 10 showed the calibration line obtained from specimen 9. It should be noted that at the edge of the specimen, averaged brightness is not the same as that in central area of the specimen because of the nature of the X-ray CT. Therefore we used different calibration line for the edge of the specimen.

Fig. 10 Calibration line between average brightness and $V_f/(V_f+V_m)$ ratio

After elastic constants calculation, we rotated principal axis of the material so that the first principal axis is along to the fiber direction measured by the method described in section 2.1. It should be noted that the elastic constants calculation and rotation were performed for element by element. Therefore in this method, each element had different stiffness matrix, which reflected the effect of the voids and fiber distortion. The finite element analyses were performed using commercial finite element code ABAQUS/Standard 6.13. Elastic constants calculation and material axis rotation were introduced using user subroutines UMAT and ORIENT, respectively.

3.3 Results and Discussion

Four-point bending tests were carried out with fifteen specimens including TP1, TP2 and TP3. Tests were based on ASTM D6272-02 although some parameters were out of ASTM specification because of the specimen size. The distance between loading points was one third of that between supporting points and displacement transducer was put under the middle of the specimen to measure the maximum deflection. Photograph of the test and the results are shown in Fig. 11. Bending modulus E_b of each specimen was calculated by,

$$y_{\max} = -23PL^3/1296EI \quad (6)$$

where y_{\max} means maximum deflection, P means applied load, L means span, and I means area moment of inertia. From eq.(6), bending modulus of the specimens TP1, TP2, TP3 were 73.2 GPa, 81.1 GPa, 70.7 GPa, respectively.

Simulations of the four point bending tests were performed by using the method described in the previous section. Figure 12 illustrates the simulation model. Fixture of the four point bending test was modeled by rigid surface. By using applied load and the maximum deflection, simulated bending moduli were calculated by eq.(6). Calculated bending moduli of TP1, TP2, TP3 models were 72.7 GPa, 63.4 GPa, 70.1 GPa, respectively.

Simulated bending moduli for TP1 and TP3 agreed very well with experimentally measured ones. As for TP1, the model with considering voids and without considering fiber misalignment, and the one without considering voids or fiber misalignment were also conducted. The calculated bending moduli were 80.8 GPa, 97.8 GPa, respectively. The results actually indicated the deterioration of bending modulus caused by microscopic defects. The results proved that the proposed method could successfully simulate the effect of the microscopic defect on the bending modulus.

Fig. 11 Four-point bending test and the results of TP1, TP2 and TP3

Fig. 12 Overview of the simulation of the four-point bending test

On the other hand, simulated bending modulus of TP2 was significantly lower than that measured by experiments. One possible reason of this difference is the calculation of the volume fraction. For TP2, V_f was calculated by calibration line illustrated in Fig. 10. However, there is large scatter in the relationship between the $V_f/(V_f+V_m)$ ratio and averaged brightness. When we calculated the bending modulus using the upper limit of the $V_f/(V_f+V_m)$ -brightness relationship illustrated in Fig. 13, the calculated modulus of TP2 was 78.9 GPa, which was close to the experimental result 81.1 GPa.

Another possible reason of the difference of the results of TP2 is the selection of the region scanned by X-ray CT. We chose three regions illustrated in Fig. 9 for X-ray CT scanning, although it is desirable to scan the whole model because scanning time becomes too long. In order to perform precise calculation, we may have to scan the whole specimen.

Fig. 13 Another calibration line between average brightness and $V_f/(V_f+V_m)$ ratio

4 CONCLUSION

This study aimed to develop a method to measure the microscopic defects in CFRP laminates from X-ray CT images and a method to introduce the effect of the defects to the finite element method. In the method, voids and fiber distortion were considered. Voids were detected using the difference of the

brightness of the X-ray CT images. Fiber distortion was analyzed by processing acquired tomographic images by digital image correlation method (DIC). The effect of the voids and fiber distortion were introduced to the commercial finite element code by using user subroutines. The proposed method was applied to the CFRP lattice cylindrical structure for future launch vehicle. The comparison between the simulated results and experimental results proved that the proposed method can simulate the effect of the microscopic defects on the material properties. However, for one specimen, the proposed method did not simulate the property precisely. In order to perform precise calculation, the method to determine fiber volume fraction has to be improved, and the method to choose the X-ray CT scanning region has to be discussed further.

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REFERENCES

- [1] T. Centea, L.K. Grunenfelder, S.R. Nutt, A review of out-of-autoclave prepregs – Material properties, process phenomena, and manufacturing considerations, *Composites Part A*, **70**, 2015, pp.132-154.
- [2] W. Li, J. Krehl, J. W. Gillespie, Jr. and D. Heider, Process and Performance Evaluation of the Vacuum-Assisted Process, *Journal of Composite Material*, **38**, 2004, pp. 1803-1814.
- [3] V. V. Vasiliev, V. A. Barynin, A. F. Rasin, Anisogrid lattice structures – survey of development and application, *Composite Structures*, **54**, 2001, pp. 361-370.
- [4] V. V. Vasiliev, A. F. Rasin, Anisogrid composite lattice structures for spacecraft and aircraft applications, *Composite Structures*, **76**, 2006, pp. 182-189.
- [5] V. V. Vasiliev, V. A. Barynin, A. F. Rasin, Anisogrid composite lattice structures – Development and aerospace applications, *Composite Structures*, **94**, 2012, pp. 1117-1127.
- [6] T. Aoki, T. Yokozeki, S. Yoshino, K. Terashima, T. Kamita, Mechanical Behavior of Composite Lattice Cylinders, *55th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/SC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, National Harbor, Maryland*, January 13-17, 2014.
- [7] B. Budiansky, N. A. Fleck, Compressive failure of fibre composites, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **41**, 1993, pp. 183-211.
- [8] S. D. Green, M. Y. Matveev, A. C. Long, D. Ivanov, S. R. Hallett, Mechanical modelling of 3D woven composites considering realistic unit cell geometry, *Composites Structures*, 2014, **118**, pp. 284-293.
- [9] M. W. Czabaj, M. L. Riccio, W. W. Whitacre, Numerical reconstruction of graphite/epoxy composite microstructure based on sub-micron resolution X-ray computed tomography, *Composites Science and Technology*, **105**, 2014, pp. 174-182.
- [10] A. Yoshimura, R. Hosoya, J. Koyanagi, T. Ogasawara, X-ray computed tomography used to measure fiber orientation in CFRP laminates, *Advanced Composite Materials*, in-print (DOI:10.1080/09243046.2014.959240).
- [11] S. Yoneyama, Displacement and Strain Measurement Using Digital Image Correlation, *Journal of N.D.I.*, **59**, 2010, pp. 306–310 (in Japanese).